

Generalized anxiety disorder associated with individual work performance of Indonesian medical personnel during COVID-19 outbreak

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ABSTRACT

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak has the potential to affect the mental health of medical personnel. This study aimed to investigate the anxiety experienced by medical personnel during the COVID-19 outbreak and its correlation with individual work performance. A cross-sectional study was conducted on 501 Medical Personnel in Indonesia. Anxiety level and work performance were assessed by the GAD-7 and IWP-1.0. Data analysis techniques used were descriptive statistics, Man-Whitney test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation. The results showed that 33.33% of the participants did not experience anxiety, followed by moderate, mild, and severe levels (31.14%, 27.74%, and 7.78%). Furthermore, the level of anxiety was different in terms of sex, age, and type of medical personnel, while there was no difference in the length of time of work. The results of the correlation analysis showed that anxiety was correlated with task performance and contextual performance, but there was no correlation with the counter-productive work behavior. There is a crucial need for psychological assistance to medical personnel in orders to reduce their anxiety as well as improve their performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the world's attention is focused on handling COVID-19. This disease is confirmed as an acute respiratory infection caused by the novel Coronavirus [1], with symptoms including fever, fatigue, dry cough, dyspnea, with or without nasal congestion, runny nose or other upper respiratory symptoms [2]. Up to August 24, 2020 there are 23,057,288 confirmed cases with 800,906 confirmed death spread over 216 countries [3]. Due to the danger of this outbreak, on January 30, 2020 the WHO declared an international health emergency [4].

Inevitably, the outbreak of the virus caused a significant impact on many aspects, such as the economy, tourism, work, social, and Education. COVID 19 also causes people to experience mental health problems. Information broadcast by the media regarding the dangers of COVID-19 and the unavailability of a vaccine causes psychosomatic symptoms in the community. Especially in Indonesia, the panic over this

outbreak in the early days caused other significant impacts, such as the lack of availability of masks and hand sanitizers [5, 6].

Anxiety can be experienced by each individual with varying intensities. Anxiety can be understood as a pathological part of normal fear, manifested by mood disorders such as thoughts, behavior and physiological activities [7]. Anxiety disorders (generalized anxiety disorder, agoraphobia, and social anxiety disorder) are the most common psychiatric disorders and are associated with a high burden of illness [8]. Anxiety disorders are often under recognized and not dealt with quickly [8]. A research reveals that generalized anxiety disorder causes the quality of life to decrease [9]. Besides, anxiety can also cause other health problems, such as heart disease [10]. Several dimensions of anxiety disorder include chronic, excessive and uncontrollable worry about multiple topics [11].

Several studies have shown that COVID-19 has affected the anxiety of the general public and certain groups. This pandemic affects the psychological aspects of college students [12], teachers and students [13], presents a major mental health challenge to older adults [14], young adult [15], and internal migrant worker [16]. COVID-19 also has a significant impact on the anxiety of medical personnel [17-19].

A study revealed that nurses who co-treat COVID-19 patients showed stimulation/sensitivity, irritability, reluctance to rest, and signs of psychological disorders, but refuse psychological help and claim that they do not have any problems [20]. Medical personnel are also concerned about a lack of personal protective equipment, as well as a feeling of being unable to treat critical patients [20]. They face a high level of stress, including a high risk of contracting, overwork, frustration, discrimination, isolation, dealing with patients with negative emotions, intense family relationships, and fatigue [21]. It is predicted that this anxiety disorder can interfere with the work performance of health workers, especially when dealing with COVID-19 patients.

Several studies reveal that the anxiety experienced by workers has a correlation with several dimensions of work performance [22-25]. Work performance consists of explicit job behavior that includes the fundamental job responsibilities assigned as part of the job description [26]. Performance standards are set based on job criteria that explain what the organization has given its employees to do, therefore individual performance in job criteria must be measured, compared with existing standards and the results must be notified to all employees. Several aspects of work performance were expressed by several experts, including creativity, reactivity in the face of difficulties, interpersonal adaptability, training efforts, and handling work-related stress. In addition, other concepts also mention aspects of task performance, contextual performance, and counter-productive work behavior [27]. Task performance is an individual's proficiency in performing core or technical tasks in his job [28]; contextual performance is behavior that supports the organizational, social and psychological environment in which the technical core must function [29]; on the other hand, counterproductive work behavior is behavior that harms the well-being of the organization [30]. These three dimensions then form the basis for preparing the Individual Work Performance questionnaire [27].

Currently, it is very important to know in detail about the anxiety experienced by medical personnel, so that it can be used as a basis for psychological intervention on them. In particular, this study aimed to: 1) evaluate the anxiety experienced by medical personnel when dealing with COVID-19; 2) as a theoretical basis for providing psychological intervention to medical personnel; 3) as material for policy making by the government related to improving the mental health of medical personnel.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Study design and participants

A cross-sectional survey used in this study aimed to measure anxiety and individual work performance of health workers from June 17, 2020 to July 25, 2020. Participants in this study were medical personnel in Indonesia who were handling suspected and confirmed COVID-19 cases, which are classified into three groups, namely doctors, nurses, and other health workers (midwifery personnel, pharmaceutical technical personnel, biomedical engineering personnel). A total of 501 participants participated in filling out this questionnaire. Table 1 shows the demographic and other special characteristics.

Demographic characteristics and other special characteristics can be seen in Table 1. Women who participated in filling out this questionnaire were 57.5%, while men were 42.5%; Furthermore, in the age factor, the most participating age groups were 21-25 (45.5%), followed by the 26-35, 36-45 and 46-55 age groups, respectively 41.5%, 10.8% and 2.2%; On the characteristics of the type of workforce, nurses dominate 41.9%, followed by doctors and other health workers (37.5% and 20.6%); on the characteristics of the length of work, more dominated by health workers whose work period was <4 years (59.9%), then sequentially 4-8 years, 9-13 years, 14-18 years, 19-23 years and >23 years, namely 22.3 %, 10.0%, 5.2%, 1.4% and 1.2%; lastly, 51.90% of participants worked at referral hospitals for COVID-19 patients, while 48.10% of participants worked for hospitals or clinics that were not a referral for COVID-19 patients.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics and specific characteristics of participants

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	213	42.51
	Female	288	57.48
Age	21-25	228	45.51
	26-35	208	41.52
	36-45	54	10.79
	46-55	11	2.19
Types of medical personnel	Doctor	188	37.52
	Nurse	210	41.92
	Other medical personnel	103	20.56
length of working experience	Less than 4 Years	300	59.88
	4-8 Years	112	22.36
	9-13 Years	50	9.98
	14-18 Years	26	5.19
	19-23 Years	7	1.40
Hospital type	More than 23 Years	6	1.20
	A referral for COVID-19 patients	260	51.90
	Not a referral for COVID-19 patients	241	48.10

2.2. Instruments

2.2.1. Generalized anxiety disorder scale (GAD-7)

The Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale (GAD-7) used in this study aimed to measure the anxiety experienced by participants. This instrument measures the anxiety symptoms experienced by participants related to COVID-19 in the past two weeks. GAD-7 consists of seven items using four Likert scale options, namely 0= not at all, 1= several days, 2= more than half the days, and 3= nearly every day. GAD-7 norms are interpreted as: minimal (0-4), mild (5-9), moderate (10-14) and severe (14-20). This scale is reported to be reliable and valid for measuring anxiety in both general and special groups [31, 32]. We use this scale in the Indonesian version. Internal validity and reliability for Indonesian version of GAD-7 were satisfactory with validity coefficient of 0.648 to 0.800 ($p < 0.01$) and Cronbach's alpha value of 0.867 [32].

2.2.2. Individual work performance questionnaire

In this study, Work performance was measured using the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IWP-1.0) [33]. This questionnaire consists of 18 items. All items had a recall period of 3 months. This scale consists of 3 dimensions, namely task performance (TP) consisting of 5 items, contextual performance (CP) consisting of 8 items and counterproductive work behavior (CWB) consisting of eight items [33]. This questionnaire uses a five-choice Likert scale (TP and CP: seldom, sometimes, regularly, often, always; CWB: never, seldom, sometimes, regularly, often). This questionnaire has a high coefficient of reliability and validity; the reliability coefficient for task performance is 0.78, contextual performance is 0.85, and counter-productive work behavior is 0.79 [34].

2.3. Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 24. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages, mean, and standard deviation) were used to describe general health worker anxiety as well as based on demographic and other special characteristics. Multivariate analysis of health worker anxiety in terms of gender using the Man-Whitney test, while Kruskal-Wallis are used to reveal differences in anxiety in terms of other characteristics. Furthermore, Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation is used to determine the relationship between generalized anxiety disorder and individual dimensions of work performance (task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

Table 2 shows that 33.33% of participants did not experience anxiety disorders (minimal), then 31.14% of participants experienced moderate levels of anxiety disorder, followed by mild and severe levels of 27.74% and 7.78%. Furthermore, Table 3 explains the differences in anxiety in terms of gender, age, type of medical personnel, and length of work experience. The results of the analysis show that: 1) there is a difference in anxiety in terms of gender ($p < .000$), where the average score of women's anxiety is higher than that of men with an average score of 8.43 and 6.47. 2) there is a difference in anxiety in terms of age ($p < 0.009$). Table 2 shows that the highest level of anxiety was experienced by medical personnel aged 21-25 with an average score of 8.40, while the lowest level of anxiety was experienced by the 46-45 age group. 3)

there are differences in anxiety between doctors, nurses and other medical personnel ($p < 0.017$); The highest level of anxiety was experienced by nurses with an average score of 8.50, followed by doctors and other health workers (midwifery staff, pharmaceutical technicians, biomedical engineering workers) at 7.21 and 6.67, respectively. 4) There is no difference in anxiety seen from the length of work experience ($p > 0.222$). However, medical personnel whose work tenure is less experienced a higher level of anxiety than those who have worked for a long time. 5) There is a difference in anxiety between medical personnel who work at referral hospitals for COVID-19 patients and medical personnel who work in hospitals or clinics that are not referrals for COVID-19 patients ($p < 0.000$); medical personnel who work at referral hospitals for COVID-19 patients experience higher anxiety.

Table 2. Respondents with different anxiety level (n=501)

Anxiety level	Number of participants	Percentage (%)	Mean	Standard deviation
Minimal	167	33.33	1.63	1.40
Mild	139	27.74	7.11	1.36
Moderate	156	31.14	12.33	1.43
Severe	39	7.78	16.51	1.29

Table 3. Univariate analysis of health workers' anxiety about the COVID-19 outbreak

Variable	Total (%)	Mean (SD)	Anxiety level				Statistics	p
			Minimal	Mild	Moderate	Severe		
Gender								
Male	213 (42.51)	6.57 (4.91)	84 (39.44)	67 (31.45)	52 (24.41)	10 (4.69)	-4.050 ^a	.000
Female	288 (57.48)	8.43 (5.28)	83 (28.82)	72 (25.00)	116 (40.28)	17 (5.90)		
AGE							6.844 ^b	.009
21-25	228 (45.51)	8.40 (5.06)	67 (29.38)	51 (22.39)	100 (43.86)	10 (4.38)		
26-35	208 (41.52)	7.22 (5.39)	77 (37.02)	61 (29.33)	56 (26.92)	14 (6.73)		
36-45	54 (10.78)	6.48 (5.01)	19 (35.18)	20 (37.04)	12 (22.22)	3 (5.55)		
46-55	11 (2.19)	5.54 (2.88)	4 (36.36)	7 (63.64)	0 (0)	0 (0)		
Types of medical personnel							5.740 ^b	.017
Doctor	188 (37.52)	7.21 (4.79)	61 (32.45)	62 (32.98)	60 (31.91)	5 (2.66)		
Nurse	210 (41.92)	8.50 (5.52)	61 (29.05)	53 (25.24)	74 (35.24)	22 (10.48)		
Other medical personnel	103 (20.56)	6.67 (5.03)	45 (43.70)	24 (23.30)	34 (33.01)	0 (0)		
Length of work experience							1.492 ^b	.222
< 4 Years	300 (59.89)	7.58 (5.24)	107 (35.67)	80 (26.67)	101 (33.67)	15 (5.00)		
4-8 Years	112 (22.35)	8.31 (5.17)	30 (26.78)	29 (25.89)	42 (37.50)	8 (7.14)		
9-13 Years	50 (9.99)	7.72 (5.27)	14 (28.00)	17 (34.00)	17 (34.00)	2 (4.00)		
14-18 Years	26 (5.19)	6.46 (5.29)	11 (42.31)	7 (26.92)	6 (23.08)	2 (7.69)		
19-23 Years	7 (1.40)	6.00 (4.69)	3 (42.86)	2 (28.57)	2 (28.57)	0 (0)		
>23 Years	6 (1.20)	5.00 (2.00)	2 (33.33)	4 (66.67)	0 (0)	0 (0)		
Hospital type								
A referral for COVID-19 patients	260 (51.90)	8.65 (5.31)	66 (25.38)	64 (24.61)	98 (37.69)	31 (11.92)	-4.307 ^a	.000
Not a referral for COVID-19 patients	241 (48.10)	6.56 (4.86)	100 (41.49)	75 (31.12)	58 (24.07)	8 (3.32)		

a. Mann-Whitney test

b. Kruskal-Wallis test

The results of the correlation analysis between generalized anxiety disorders experienced by medical personnel in Indonesia with the individual dimensions of work performance are shown in Table 4. Anxiety has a negative correlation with task performance ($r = -.133$) and contextual performance ($r = -.103$), while the correlation with the dimensions of counter-productive work behavior ($r = -.060$) was not found.

Table 4. Correlation between generalized anxiety disorder and individual dimensions of work performance (task performance, contextual performance, counter-productive work behavior)

GAD	Individual work performance dimensions		
	Task performance	Contextual performance	Counter productive work behavior
	-.133**	-.103*	-.060

Note: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

3.2. Discussion

Anxiety during the COVID-19 outbreak is experienced by both the general and specific population. A survey on general public anxiety about COVID-19 in America, found that 48% of participants were worried about contracting COVID-19 and 59% stated that COVID-19 was affecting their lives [35]. Another study revealed that more than 50% of participants experienced anxiety and psychological distress during this pandemic [36]. One of the causes of public anxiety regarding COVID-19 is due to the almost constant flow of news about COVID-19. Therefore, WHO recommends avoiding news about COVID-19 that makes you uncomfortable, especially hoax news about COVID-19 [37].

The results of this study indicated that 31.14% of medical personnel experienced a moderate level of anxiety, followed by mild and severe levels, namely 27.74% and 7.78%; relevant to the findings of previous studies which revealed that medical personnel experience anxiety during this pandemic [17-19]. The anxiety experienced during the COVID-19 outbreak by medical personnel has been mixed. In comparison, a study of health workers in Peru showed greater anxiety, with 21.7% of medical personnel experienced severe anxiety during this outbreak. [18]. However, there are studies which reveal that only a small proportion of medical personnel experience extremely severe anxiety [19]. Participants who experienced moderate and severe levels of anxiety generally worked at referral hospitals for COVID-19 patients in Indonesia, while participants who were at a mild level were those who worked in hospitals, health centers, and health clinics who did not directly handle COVID-19 patients, but still has the potential to become the first health center visited by patients with symptoms of COVID-19. This findings may indeed be relevant to previous studies that found that medical personnel employed in the outpatient pandemic clinic + pandemic department experience greater anxiety than medical personnel employed only in the outpatient pandemic clinic or department [38].

The anxiety experienced by medical personnel is because they have the potential to contract COVID-19 from patients. Even some cases of death due to COVID-19 have come from medical personnel. As of July 20, 2020, 821 health workers in America have died from COVID-19 [39]; The Indonesian Doctors Association also reported that 68 doctors died [40], this does not include other medical personnel. Many sacrifices have been made by medical personnel in helping the handling of COVID-19 patients, such as experiencing facial wounds due to using N95 masks for too long, using diapers while working, not eating and drinking to save personal protective equipment, even among health workers who cut their hair in order to reduce the risk of contracting it. In the absence of personal protective equipment, the number of tasks that must be completed, facing various patient characteristics, isolation, etc., they are still required to perform high work performance.

The univariate analysis shows that there are differences in medical personnel anxiety in terms of gender, in which women experience higher anxiety than men; these findings support previous research [41, 42]. Female consistently has a higher prevalence of anxiety disorders, but little is known about how gender affects age of onset, chronicity, comorbidity, and burden of illness [43]. In women, generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) has a positive correlation with depression symptoms and loneliness, while in men it has correlation with somatic symptoms [44]. Anxiety also differed significantly in terms of age. The participants who filled out this questionnaire consisted of several age groups. Starting from those who have just entered the world of work to enter retirement. These findings indicate that anxiety is highest in the 21-25 age group, followed by the 26-35, 36-45 and 46-55 age groups. Several studies have shown that younger individuals show symptoms of anxiety than older people [18, 41, 45]; supported by the finding that older person has a lower current and lifetime social anxiety disorder [46].

In terms of the type of medical personnel (doctors, nurses and other medical personnel), nurses obtained a higher anxiety score than doctors and other medical personnel; relevant to previous research [47]. A study shows there is a difference in anxiety between medical staff and other medical workers [48]. The same result was revealed through a study that compared to doctors, nurses were under higher pressure in handling COVID-19 [49]. In this study, only the characteristics of the length of work experience did not determine the differences in anxiety among participants; these findings support other studies [50]. However, the scores for medical personnel who worked <8 years were higher than those who had worked longer hours. As a comparison, one of the causes of the higher anxiety symptoms experienced by young doctors is direct exposure and longer working hours; senior doctors act as advisors and main administrative responsibility, so there is less contact with COVID-19 patients [51]. However, this condition is not always the same between hospitals and countries.

The results of the correlation analysis show a negative relationship between anxiety and the two dimensions of individual work performance (task performance and contextual performance), while there is no correlation with the dimensions of counter-productive work behavior. Individual work performance is a multidimensional construct. Of these three constructs, there are two positive dimensions, namely task performance (TP) and contextual performance (CP), while counter-productive work behavior (CWB) is a

behavior that hinders organizational goals. The lower the anxiety experienced by the participants, the higher the TP and CP dimensions, and vice versa. This supports research which reveals that contextual performance is closely related with burnout [22]; In relation to CT, Individuals with GAD evidenced impaired performance on an attention vigilance task [23]. Previous researchers have also investigated the relationship between mental health and counter work behavior. A study revealed that job stress is correlated with CWB [24]. Stress conditions are specifically associated with negative emotions, aggression and CWB [52]. This is supported by other findings which say that pressure at work can not only cause CWB, but also cause negative employee effectiveness [25].

The current condition demands that every medical personnel receive intensive attention, especially from the government, such as the provision of physical facilities, personal protective equipment, psychological intervention, providing nutritious food, rest time arrangements, incentives, and support from those closest to them. Barriers such as high anxiety in dealing with COVID-19 patients must be reduced so that work performance is good. Barriers to implementing workplace practices can weaken employee commitment to the organization which is positively related to work performance.

There were several limitations to our study. First, this measurement was carried out by cross sectional without any follow-up through a longitudinal study. The case of COVID-19 which continues to experience changes may have an impact on changes in the anxiety conditions experienced by health workers. In addition, data on the anxiety experienced by medical personnel prior to the COVID-19 outbreak were not available, making it difficult to know whether the anxiety conditions they were experiencing were influenced by conditions before the outbreak. Second, this questionnaire is self-assessment, so it may differ from psychological assessments conducted by professionals. Third, the questionnaire was distributed through WhatsApp groups with members of medical personnel in Indonesia. We still have difficulty getting data from medical personnel in eastern Indonesia; Besides that, difficulties were also experienced when they wanted to collect data from specialist doctors who were busy handling COVID-19 patients.

4. CONCLUSION

Medical personnel have felt anxiety during the COVID-19 outbreak, especially those who are treating positive patients. This increase in cases is predicted to have an effect on the increase in the number of health workers experiencing mental health problems, especially since there are still many health facilities that do not meet standards, unavailability of vaccines, scarcity of personal protective equipment, lack of rest time, and strict activity rules for them. Of course, these problems will affect work performance. Based on this condition, psychological intervention is needed for medical personnel who are in charge of handling COVID-19 patients, providing complete health facilities and personal protective equipment, and most importantly finding a vaccine for this disease as soon as possible.

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